

THE CONCEPT OF GENDER EQUALITY AND THE IMPORTANCE OF GENDER EQUALITY IN SCHOOL EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

Yunusova Xolida

National research institute named Abdulla Avlaniy, doctoral student

xolidayunusova124@gmail.com

Abstract: Improving the quality of education in schools is directly related to the effective organization of the activities of the school director. This article highlights the managerial competence of a leader and measures for its development. Some comments are given on the nature of the concept of gender that is often encountered today and the importance of the gender aspect in educational management.

Key words: educational management, managerial competence, gender, gender equality, gender stereotypes.

Gender is defined as a complex, multi-layered social practice that differentiates men and women, masculinity and femininity through formal and informal power processes. (Van Den Brink, Holgersson, Linghag and Dee, 2016)

One explanation for this complexity is given by Marx through evolution into a complex system. This evolution leads to more distinct differences in the body and reason between women and men, specialized roles and the division of labor. Process by which this social process is carried out is called socialization. Socialization is carried out manifests itself in the early stages of a person's life through the family. This socialization is carried out through education (school system) and society in the future constantly. (Holmes, 2007) The 19th century witnessed the beginning of gender equality in the Nordic countries. From then, it has seen important developments during the whole of the 20th century in different parts of the world with different levels of achievement, results and consequences based on country, industry, age and seniority. The different influencing factors of gender equality varies based on the setting like the consequences of achievement or lack thereof. The concept of gender equality is assumed to have fundamental differences between the western philosophies and eastern philosophies. This has obvious influences on the performance of different countries. One of the fundamental and well-known methods to compare different countries is through Hofstede's cultural dimensions where one of the dimensions of masculinity have a relationship with the concept of gender equality. (Hofstede, Hofstede & Minkov, 2005) The early works on gender equality focused on fundamental aspects such as education and primary health care. This has led to considerable developments on the quality of life in developed countries although a lot is to be achieved in the world in general. This is evident with Goal 5 of the Sustainable development challenges of

the 21st century being Gender equality. It has taken several decades to achieve a situation where equality is achieved in the fundamental aspects. (Le Blanc, 2012) Gender equality refers to the equal rights, responsibilities, and opportunities of all individuals, regardless of their gender. It is a fundamental human right and a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable world. Despite significant progress in recent years, gender inequality remains a pervasive issue across the globe.

In many societies, women and girls continue to face discrimination and marginalization in various aspects of life, including education, employment, healthcare, and political representation. This inequality not only violates their basic human rights but also hinders social and economic development.

One of the key areas where gender inequality is most evident is in the workforce. Women are often paid less than men for the same work and are underrepresented in leadership positions. This wage gap not only affects individual women but also has broader implications for families and communities. Additionally, women are often confined to low-paying and insecure jobs, limiting their economic empowerment and independence.

Education is another critical area where gender inequality persists. Despite progress in increasing girls' access to education, disparities still exist, particularly in developing countries. Many girls are denied the opportunity to attend school due to cultural norms, poverty, or lack of resources. As a result, they are deprived of the knowledge and skills necessary to improve their lives and contribute to their communities.

Furthermore, gender-based violence continues to be a significant barrier to achieving gender equality. Women and girls are disproportionately affected by various forms of violence, including domestic abuse, sexual assault, and human trafficking. These experiences not only cause physical and emotional harm but also limit women's ability to participate fully in society.

Addressing gender inequality requires coordinated efforts at the local, national, and international levels. Governments, civil society organizations, and individuals must work together to promote gender equality through policy reforms, awareness campaigns, and advocacy initiatives.

Empowering women and girls is essential for achieving gender equality. This includes ensuring access to quality education, promoting economic opportunities, and protecting their rights. It also involves challenging harmful gender stereotypes and promoting positive representations of women in media and popular culture.

Additionally, engaging men and boys as allies in the fight for gender equality is crucial. By challenging traditional notions of masculinity and promoting respect for women's rights, we can create more inclusive and equitable societies.

Ultimately, achieving gender equality is not only a matter of justice but also a prerequisite for sustainable development and social progress. By working towards a world where all individuals have equal opportunities and rights, we can create a more just and prosperous future for everyone.

Gender equality is a fundamental human right that is essential for the development and progress of any society. In the context of school education leadership, ensuring gender equality is not only a matter of fairness but also a strategic imperative. The presence of diverse perspectives and experiences in leadership roles is crucial for creating inclusive, innovative, and effective educational environments. Therefore, addressing gender disparities in school leadership is critical for promoting a more equitable and enriching learning experience for all students.

First and foremost, promoting gender equality in school education leadership is essential for providing role models and mentors for students. When students see women in leadership positions within their schools, they are more likely to envision themselves in similar roles in the future. This representation is crucial for breaking down gender stereotypes and empowering both girls and boys to pursue their aspirations without limitations based on gender.

Furthermore, diverse leadership teams bring a range of perspectives and approaches to problem-solving and decision-making. Research has shown that diverse teams are more effective at addressing complex challenges and fostering creativity and innovation. By ensuring gender equality in school leadership, educational institutions can benefit from a wider range of insights and ideas, ultimately enhancing the quality of education and the overall school environment.

In addition, promoting gender equality in school leadership can help address systemic barriers that perpetuate gender inequality in education. Women leaders are often more attuned to the specific needs and challenges faced by female students, such as addressing gender-based discrimination, promoting girls' participation in STEM fields, and supporting initiatives to combat gender-based violence. By having women in leadership roles, schools can implement policies and programs that create a more inclusive and supportive environment for all students.

Moreover, achieving gender equality in school leadership can contribute to the professional development and advancement of female educators. By providing equal opportunities for women to assume leadership positions, schools can foster a more diverse pool of talent and expertise. This not only benefits individual educators but also contributes to the overall improvement of the education system by harnessing a broader range of skills and experiences.

It is important to recognize that achieving gender equality in school education leadership requires deliberate efforts to address systemic barriers and biases. This includes implementing policies to promote equal representation in leadership positions,

providing mentorship and professional development opportunities for aspiring female leaders, and challenging traditional gender norms within educational institutions.

Additionally, engaging male educators and administrators as allies in the promotion of gender equality is crucial. By fostering a culture of respect and support for women's leadership, schools can create an environment where all individuals are empowered to contribute their unique perspectives and talents.

In conclusion, the importance of gender equality in school education leadership cannot be overstated. By promoting equal representation and opportunities for women in leadership roles, educational institutions can create more inclusive, innovative, and effective learning environments. Ultimately, by embracing diverse perspectives and experiences, schools can better prepare students for success in an increasingly diverse and interconnected world. It is imperative that we continue to advocate for gender equality in school leadership to ensure that every student has the opportunity to thrive and reach their full potential.

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